

Pi Chamber Mixed-Phase Cloud Simulation Case

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Related papers to cite:

1. Wang, A., Krueger, S., Chen, S., Ovchinnikov, M., Cantrell, W., and Shaw, R. A.: Glaciation of mixed-phase clouds: insights from bulk model and bin-microphysics large-eddy simulation informed by laboratory experiment, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 24, 10245–10260, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-24-10245-2024>, 2024.
2. Wang, A., Chen, S., Krueger, P., Dziekan, K., Enokido, F., Hoffmann, A., Makulska, B., Mehlig, S., Schmalfuß, G., Sarnistky, S., Shima, F., Yang, M., Ovchinnikov, R., Shaw: *A Model Intercomparison Study of Mixed-Phase Clouds in a Laboratory Chamber*, to be submitted. 2024

Use this link to google doc to get the most up-to-date version:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Q_I0hx31kulrDalFoezJGIQTEVyBYBtNVQuhSomBfZc/edit?usp=sharing

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Timeline

Oct 2023	Announcements & invitations
Dec 20, 2023	Confirmation of participation
May 1, 2024	Results received from the participants
May-June 2024	Data post-processing & communication with participants
July 8-12 2024	International Cloud Modeling Workshop in Seoul
Post workshop	Paper summarizing the case

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Contact us if interested in joining the group mailing address:
icmw2024-pi-chamber-case@googlegroups.com (we will communicate through this channel before the workshop)

Acknowledgment and Authorship

We would like to highlight that the team, along with the Pi Chamber group, has dedicated significant time and effort to set up and prepare this case.

In the spirit of recognizing our collective contribution and effort, we kindly request that if you are considering publishing a paper based on this case, please consider including the case coordinators (Aaron Wang, Steven Krueger, and Sisi Chen) and the Pi Chamber group (Raymond Shaw and Neel Desai) as co-authors.

We believe that collaborative efforts deserve collaborative recognition, and your understanding and cooperation in this regard would be greatly appreciated.

Updates on case description:

May 14, 2024 [1. correct the esp value to 0.622 for computing supersaturation in [section 1.2](#); 2. correct the ice mass growth equation in [Model configuration Table 1.3](#)]

April 8, 2024. [1. Update the values obtained from SAM LES in [section 1.2](#); 2. Added more descriptions to the 1D output variables on [1D data Section](#) The liquid mass removal rate in the output session should include all liquid phase particles for budget analysis.]

Feb 14, 2024. [Update the SAM LES wall model to the latest version. The SAM LES example is updated (after matching μ and σ , the side-wall wetness w.r.t ice is **0.30 instead of 0.52**). The suggested values in [Section 1.2](#) are slightly affected.]

Jan 3, 2024. (use $r_{threshold} = 3.5 \mu m$ for both the droplet critical radius and the threshold droplet radius to calculate mean droplet radius, for simplicity, see [1.3](#); added LWC and IWC in [Model Output table 2.1](#) as required 2D model output (vertical profile).)

Dec. 17. 2023 (added equations for droplet/ice growth in [Model configuration Table 1.3](#).)

Case overview

Motivation

- This work is a continuation of the prior ICMW Pi Chamber study focused on warm-phase cases (Krueger et al. 2022). The current exploration focuses on mixed-phase processes.
- While the preceding study concentrated on the steady-state of warm clouds in the Pi Chamber, emphasizing the behavior of warm microphysics – from droplet size distribution shapes, droplet number concentrations, and mean radius to the responses and fluctuations of supersaturation due to varying aerosol injection rates – this study shifts its gaze towards a even more mysterious area: mixed-phase microphysics.
- The intricacy of processes associated with ice remains insufficiently understood at their native scales. In cloud modeling, considerable uncertainty arises from microphysical parameterizations. Further complicating the situation, the data sets meant for formulating and validating these parameterizations are limited. Many times, the boundary conditions for these measurements are ambiguously defined, and atmospheric systems often lack statistical stability.
- The Pi Chamber offers reasonably well-characterized boundary conditions. It is capable of achieving steady-state for a long period, supported by detailed measurements of both microphysical and thermodynamic properties – an invaluable asset for both model design and validation.
- Numerical simulations, particularly those resolving finer-scale cloud processes, bring forth a process-level understanding of microphysics, which can not be achieved in conventional cloud models.
- In the broader perspective, comparing results from high-resolution models with laboratory measurements facilitates evaluating model physics. The well-validated model in return can be used to better understand the details of physical processes that current instrumentation struggles to measure.

Objectives

- The objectives of this case study are to answer:
 - How well do models represent mixed-phase processes, in particular those processes that determine the relative amounts of (supercooled) liquid and ice in a steady-state cloud?
 - Starting from a purely supercooled liquid cloud, in the Pi Chamber, what are the resulting steady-state cloud properties under various ice nucleus injection rates?
 - What is the critical point (microphysical conditions) that cloud glaciation happens?
 - How do these properties compare to Pi Chamber measurements?
- Via model intercomparisons, we aim to ascertain:
 - What are the key differences in the results of different models when imposing the same set of constraints from laboratory measurements? What causes the differences?
 - Can we understand /mitigate the divergence between the model results?
 - What are the implications for larger-scale model representations of mixed-phase cloud processes?

Introduction to the Pi chamber facility

What is the PI Chamber?

The Pi chamber is a turbulent, multiphase reaction chamber developed at Michigan Technological University. The cloud chamber is capable of generating and sustaining cloud formation in simulated tropospheric conditions for minutes to days.

Chamber schematics & capacity

Schematics of the PI Chamber structure are illustrated below (Figure 1 and Figure 2). The pressure shell is rectangular. The internal volume is 1 m high and 2 m wide. Two front-opening hinged doors give full access to the internal workspace. The thermal panels, which regulate the temperature within the chamber, are controlled on three separate circuits, corresponding to the top, bottom, and sidewall sections of the chamber internal workspace. All panels are capable of maintaining thermostatic conditions. For more detailed technical specification, see Chang et al. (BAMS 2016) <https://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/full/10.1175/BAMS-D-15-00203.1>

FIG. 1. A cutaway schematic of the cloud chamber with one door open and the cylindrical thermal panel in place.

Fig 1: Cutaway view of the PI Chamber (Chang et al., 2016)

Fig. 2: Vertical cross-section of the PI Chamber (Chandrakar et al., 2019 QJRMS)

The chamber is also accompanied by a suite of instrumentation allowing for the generation and characterization of aerosol, ice nucleating particles, and cloud particles, measurement of thermodynamic and turbulence conditions, and sampling of particles for subsequent chemical and morphological analysis.

The research problems that can be addressed with this facility range from aerosol formation and optical properties to turbulent clouds and ice nucleation. Fig. 3 illustrates the spatial structures of aerosol and cloud drop distribution inside the chamber corresponding to different aerosol injection rates.

Fig. 3. Snapshot inside the PI Chamber in a warm-phase case (top, (Chandrakar et al. 2016 PNAS)) and formation of ice in mixed-phase case (bottom, Desai et al. 2019)

Case description

The cases proposed here are focused on cloud-aerosol-turbulence interactions in a mixed-phase cloudy environment, i.e., with supercooled liquid droplets and ice particles. Modeling results from DNS, LES, and other numerical/theoretical models are all welcome.

The **case** is provided below, with an emphasis on the *steady state properties*.

Quasi-steady-state case

Aerosols (CCN) are constantly injected with a prescribed injection rate to form a steady-state supercooled droplet size distribution (DSD) in a steady-state thermal and turbulent environment, given the thermostatic wall conditions, i.e., fixed wall temperature and near-wall humidity. The detailed numerical configurations are listed in the Section of “*Model configuration for the steady state case*.” After a steady-state supercooled liquid-only cloud is established, ice nuclei will be injected at a steady rate until a new steady state is established. **The rate of ice nuclei injection will be varied among several simulations.**

1) Model configuration

Particle collision-coalescence should be turned-off, so particles grow by condensation/deposition only. We mainly provide the configurations for DNS and LES models. Participants may adjust configurations for other types of models accordingly.

Some definitions:

Spin up and steady-state: For all models, allow for a dynamic spin-up before injecting CCN. i.e., run simulations without aerosols to let the turbulence develop (until T and Qv reach steady-state).

After the dynamic spin-up, inject CCN and run simulations until *microphysics* are in steady-state. We define that the simulation is in steady-state if both mean N_drop and R_drop reach steady-state.

After the warm-phase spin-up, injecting ice nuclei particles, again allow the simulations to reach a new steady state.

Glaciation: When ice mass fraction reaches > 90%, the cloud is defined as glaciation.

1.1) Models simulating the entire chamber environment

Note that for **DNS**, the same boundary and initial conditions as listed in the table below are applied, but some parameters and conditions such as dx and dt will be different to meet their specific CFL conditions, and for resolving more detailed dynamics and microphysics.

variables	method	values
Top, bottom, and side wall temperature	$\Delta T = 20 K$	$T_t = -16 C, T_b = 4 C, T_s = -12 C$
Pressure	Standard atmospheric pressure	P=1000hPa
Water vapor mixing ratio at the walls		<p>Top wall: saturated w.r.t. ice Bottom wall: saturated w.r.t. water</p> <p>Side wall: adjust the humidity along with CCN injection rate to get mean $r_{drop} \approx 7.75 \mu m$ (for droplets of $r_{threshold} > 3.5 \mu m$) in a steady state.</p> <p>We also aim to reach the final $N_{drop} \approx 25 cm^{-3}$, but it's optional if the model can not. (One can achieve it by adjusting the injection rate, but optional.)</p> <p>e.g., SAM LES results suggest $S_{ice} = 0.30$ at the side wall and a CCN injection rate of $10 cm^{-3} min^{-1}$. Below are the results from SAM LES. One can start from these values. Note that the results may depend on wall models.</p>

		<p>(a)</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Data for Graph (a): Mean Diameter vs. Side-Wall Wetness</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Side-Wall Wetness (%)</th> <th>CCN=10 cm⁻³ min⁻¹ (µm)</th> <th>CCN=11 cm⁻³ min⁻¹ (µm)</th> <th>CCN=12 cm⁻³ min⁻¹ (µm)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>20</td> <td>13.8</td> <td>13.5</td> <td>13.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>30</td> <td>15.2</td> <td>14.8</td> <td>14.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>40</td> <td>16.5</td> <td>16.0</td> <td>15.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>50</td> <td>17.8</td> <td>17.2</td> <td>16.8</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>(b)</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Data for Graph (b): Mean Nr vs. Side-Wall Wetness</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Side-Wall Wetness (%)</th> <th>CCN=10 cm⁻³ min⁻¹ (cm⁻³)</th> <th>CCN=11 cm⁻³ min⁻¹ (cm⁻³)</th> <th>CCN=12 cm⁻³ min⁻¹ (cm⁻³)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>20</td> <td>28.5</td> <td>31.0</td> <td>34.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>30</td> <td>25.0</td> <td>29.0</td> <td>32.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>40</td> <td>21.5</td> <td>25.0</td> <td>27.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>50</td> <td>18.5</td> <td>22.0</td> <td>25.0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Side-Wall Wetness (%)	CCN=10 cm ⁻³ min ⁻¹ (µm)	CCN=11 cm ⁻³ min ⁻¹ (µm)	CCN=12 cm ⁻³ min ⁻¹ (µm)	20	13.8	13.5	13.2	30	15.2	14.8	14.5	40	16.5	16.0	15.8	50	17.8	17.2	16.8	Side-Wall Wetness (%)	CCN=10 cm ⁻³ min ⁻¹ (cm ⁻³)	CCN=11 cm ⁻³ min ⁻¹ (cm ⁻³)	CCN=12 cm ⁻³ min ⁻¹ (cm ⁻³)	20	28.5	31.0	34.5	30	25.0	29.0	32.0	40	21.5	25.0	27.5	50	18.5	22.0	25.0
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Initial vertical T & Qv profile in the chamber	A linear (unstable) profile of T and Qv (saturated w.r.t. liquid water for bottom and ice for top) between the top and bottom walls.	$T(z) = T_b - 20 K \times z/H [K]$ $Qv(z) = Qv_b - (Qv_b - Qv_t) \times z/H [kg/kg]$																																								
Geometry of the chamber, grid spacing, and timestep	Rectangular shape ($2m \times 2m \times 1m$)	$H=1 m$ (z direction) $Lx = Ly = 2 m$ $\Delta x = 3.125 cm$ $N = 64 \times 64 \times 32$ $\Delta t = 0.02 s$																																								
Boundary conditions	For LES : By providing T and Qv at the walls, we imply that fluxes are computed using some kind of similarity conditions	DNS: No-slip boundary condition. LES: Use Monin-Obukhov Similarity Theory for top, bottom, and side walls. If MOST is not available, specify what wall functions/schemes are used. (optional) For the side walls, because the direction of buoyancy is parallel instead of perpendicular to the side walls, neglect the stratification effect (i.e., use the neutral condition).																																								

		Roughness lengths: $z_0 = 0.75 \text{ mm}$ $z_T = 0.619 z_0$ $z_{qv} = 0.756 z_0$
Model spin-up time	<p>Dynamic spin-up Spin up the model turbulence before aerosols are injected to let the turbulence be fully developed and reach reach steady-state in T and Qv</p> <hr/> <p>Liquid-phase cloud spin-up Inject aerosol (CCN) at a constant rate. Wait until steady-state is reached in N_{drop} and R_{drop}. If steady-state is not observed, then at least 1 min of spin-up time is required.</p> <p>As indicated for “water vapor mixing ratio at the walls”, adjust the side-wall wetness (humidity) and CCN injection rate ($10 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) to get mean $r_{\text{drop}} \approx 7.75 \mu\text{m}$ (for droplets of $r_{\text{threshold}} > 3.5 \mu\text{m}$).</p> <p>It will be ideal if the model can get mean $N_{\text{drop}} \approx 25 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (you can achieve it by adjusting the injection rate, but optional.)</p> <p>e.g., In SAM LES, setting a side-wall $S_{\text{ice}} = 0.30$ and CCN injection rate of $10 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ with CCN regeneration can reach $N_{\text{drop}} = 25.1 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $r_{\text{drop}} = 7.65 \mu\text{m}$. One can start from these values.</p> <hr/> <p>Mixed-phase: Continue to inject aerosol (CCN) at the same rate as in liquid-phase spin up. At the same time, inject ice crystals. Continue the simulation until the cloud is <i>glaciated</i> (ice mass fraction > 90%) and a steady-state in N_{ice} and R_{ice} is reached. If steady-state is not observed, then at least 10 min of simulation is required.</p>	
Simulation time after liquid spin-up (steady-state period)	$t > 10 \text{ min}$ for each simulation. We will use this period as well as the spin-up period for data analysis.	
Initial wind profile		$U = V = W = 0 \text{ m/s}$

Detailed information can be found in the LES study of Thomas et al. (2019):
<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019MS001670>

1.2) Models simulating the core region of the chamber

Assume homogeneous and isotropic turbulence in the core region of the PI chamber. This assumption is ideal for the spectral DNS models due to their requirement for periodicity of the boundary conditions.

For **spectral DNS models**, one may use forcing in the low wavenumber band to maintain the fluctuations of the \mathbf{v} , T , and Qv fields, see table below for detail.

For **DNS with a finite difference scheme**, we strongly encourage participants to construct the full geometry of the PI chamber with explicit wall boundary conditions (see configurations in table (1.2)).

variables	methods/calculations	values
Initial mean T , Qv , and p in the core region (before injection of aerosol and ice)	Derived from SAM's LES result (For reference: T_0 in the Pi chamber is -6.7 C)	$\bar{T}_0 = -7.52\text{ C}$ $\bar{Qv}_0 = 2.28\text{ g kg}^{-1}$ $\bar{S}_w \approx 5.97\%$ $\bar{S}_{ice} \approx 13.9\%$ $P = 1000.0\text{ hPa}$
Diagnostic mean and standard deviation of supersaturation after injecting aerosols and reaching steady-state in liquid phase	<p>The diagnostic statistics \bar{S} can be calculated based on \bar{T}_0 and \bar{Qv}_0:</p> $S \approx Qv/Qv_{sat} - 1.$ $Qv_{sat} = eps \frac{e_{sat}}{(P - e_{sat})}, eps \approx 0.622.$ $e_{sat} = 2.53 \times 10^{11} \exp(-5.42 \times 10^3/T).$ <p>cf. equation (2.12) in Rogers & Yau (1989).</p>	$\bar{S}_w \approx 0.61\%$ $\bar{S}_{ice} \approx 7.89\%$ $\sigma S_w \approx 2.07\%$ $\sigma S_{ice} \approx 1.91\%$ <p>Calculation of σS: standard deviation of spatial distribution of S at each time step, then average the σS over time.</p>
Forcing on the fluctuations and the mean of the scalar	<p>External forcing on fluctuations to maintain steady-state σT</p> <p>The intensity of the forcings are determined in the case without particles (i.e., before aerosols are injected into the chamber).</p> <p>The participants shall first conduct the</p>	$\sigma T = 0.72\text{ K}$ $\sigma Qv = 0.165 \times 10^{-3}\text{ kg/kg}$

fields (T, Qv).	& σQv	simulation without injecting aerosols to determine the forcing intensity to obtain the desired standard deviation (σ) of T and Qv fields (listed on the right). The same forcing intensity should be applied to the <i>case when aerosols are injected</i> . Forcing on scalar fields is similar to forcing on the turbulence. cf. Saito et al. (2019) or Paoli & Shariff (2009) for detail.	
	Nudge the mean T & Qv to approach \bar{T}_0 and \bar{Qv}_0	Nudge the mean value with the relaxation timescale τ (eqn (28-29) in Saito et al. 2019): $\frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{\tau} (\bar{T}(t) - \bar{T}_0) + \frac{L}{C_p} \bar{C}_d$ $\frac{\partial \bar{Qv}}{\partial t} - \frac{1}{\tau} (\bar{Qv}(t) - \bar{Qv}_0) - \bar{C}_d$ The last term on the RHS of both eqns is the condensation term	$\tau \approx 60 \text{ s}$
Turbulence level		Constrain the mean eddy dissipation rate ϵ	$\epsilon \approx 0.0066 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$
Spatial resolution Δx		The grid size is required to resolve the smallest turbulence scale (Kolmogorov length-scale, η), i.e., $k_{max} \eta > 1$. k_{max} is the maximum resolvable wavenumber. Or $\Delta x < \eta$	
Initial wind velocity mean			$\bar{U}_0 = \bar{V}_0 = \bar{W}_0 = 0 \text{ m/s}$
Model spin-up time	Dynamic spin-up	Spin up the model to reach steady-state in T and Qv before aerosols are injected	
	liquid-phase spin-up	Reach steady-state in N_drop and R_drop. If steady-state is not observed, then at least 1 min of spin-up time is required.	
	mixed-phase	Inject ice nucleating particles until steady state is reached.	
Simulated time duration after spin-ups		$t_{tot} > 10 \text{ min}$ We will use this period for data analysis.	
Domain size			$L_x = L_y = L_z = 20 \text{ cm} \times 20 \text{ cm} \times 20 \text{ cm}$

1.3) How to include droplet, aerosol, and ice processing

Definition of droplet, aerosol, ice, particle:

Aerosols are referred to those not activated (i.e., for NaCl particle with $d_{dry} = 125 \text{ nm}$, r_{wet} below the radius of $r_{threshold} = 3.5 \mu\text{m}$). (An aerosol here is CCN, not INP).

The estimated critical droplet radius of the NaCl particle for $d_{dry} = 125 \text{ nm}$ is around $r_{critical} = 1.0 \mu\text{m}$ (cf. Rogers and Yau, 1989, p.88-89), but here, we will use $r_{threshold} = 3.5 \mu\text{m}$ as the minimum droplet radius to better match the instrumentation threshold from Pi chamber observations.

Droplets are defined as those over $r_{threshold} = 3.5 \mu\text{m}$.

ice is the particle in solid phase

Particles include aerosols, droplets, and ice.

Mean & fluctuation scalar fields (T & Qv)	For DNS, same forcing for mean and fluctuations as described in (1.2)	
	For LES, same boundary conditions applied as in (1.1)	
Size of aerosol (dry)	Monodisperse	$d_{dry} = 125 \text{ nm}$ (diameter)
Chemical composition		NaCl
Aerosol injection	<p>A uniform aerosol injection on every grid box instead of in the center is encouraged, though not required if it is too difficult to implement.</p> <p>Aerosol injection rate = $10 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1} = 0.167 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Keep the injection rate constant over time.</p> <p>Adjust the sidewall (a reference number from SAM LES is side-wall $S_{ice} = 0.30$) to produce <i>mean</i> $R_{drop} \approx 7.75 \mu\text{m}$ (for droplets of $r_{threshold} > 3.5 \mu\text{m}$).</p> <p>(Optional) try to reach $N_{drop} \approx 25 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ if possible.</p>	
Initial ice particle size	monodisperse, spherical	$r_{ice} = 2 \mu\text{m}$ (radius)
Ice particle injection	<p>Initial ice radius ~ 2 micron</p> <p>We suggest trying at least 5 different ice injection rates from $0 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ to $15 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$, or even higher, to reach the glaciation (i.e., ice mass fraction reaches $> 90\%$ at the end).</p>	

	<p>(suggested injection rates: $0.0 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ $0.5 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ $1.5 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ $3.0 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ $5.0 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ $10.0 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ $15.0 \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$)</p>
Droplet & ice removal / sedimentation 2 options	<p>Drop gravitational settling velocity (Rogers & Yau, 1989): $k_1 = 1.233 \times 10^8 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ $v_{drop} = k_1 r^2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ Ice gravitational settling velocity $v_{ice} = \frac{\rho_{ice}}{\rho_{water}} k_1 r^2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $\rho_{ice} = 0.91 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ for solid ice $\rho_{water} = 1.00 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ for liquid water</p>
	<p>Simulation of the core region without walls: particle removal based on the Stokes settling: Use random droplet removal based on the probability of droplet fallout during certain time interval Δt, which is $v_{drop}/H\Delta t = k_1 r^2/H\Delta t$, $H = 1 \text{ m}$, where $k_1 r^2$ is the Stoke's Law droplet terminal velocity.</p>
	<p>Full chamber simulations: remove droplets/ice when contacting the walls</p>
Droplet/ice growth	<p>Grow by condensation and deposition only (no collision/aggregation). The ice particle is assumed to be spherical. (i.e., capacitance = r) For reference (you may use either mass or size for the growth equation): Droplet growth by condensation can follow equation (1) from Chen et al. 2020 (value for each parameter can refer to the paper):</p>

$$R \frac{dR}{dt} = \frac{S - \frac{R^3 - R_d^3}{R^3 - R_d^3(1-\kappa)} \exp\left(\frac{2\sigma_w}{R_v \rho_w T R}\right)}{\frac{\rho_w R_v T}{\epsilon_s D'} + \frac{\rho_w L_v}{K'T} \left(\frac{I_v}{R_v T} - 1\right)} f_v,$$

Ice growth by deposition can follow equation (1) from [Chen et al. 2023](#) (value for each parameter can refer to the paper):

$$\frac{dm_i}{dt} = \frac{4\pi C S_i}{\left(\frac{L_s}{R_v T} - 1\right) \frac{L_s}{K'T} + \frac{R_v T}{e_{sat,i} D'}}$$

Model output

1. Data Format

The model output should be submitted in **NetCDF** format, or as an **ASCII file** with code (in Fortran, python or matlab) to read the file(s) or with reading instructions. The output variables are listed in the tables below with the requested **units**.

Output from each aerosol injection scenario should be saved in separate files.

2. Output Variables

1) 1D data (for all models):

1.1) Time series of domain-averaged statistics (Please **include the spin-up periods**)

Frequency: every 1s.

Please calculate the **domain average value** *excluding 4 points or 12.5cm from the wall*.

Output variables	Output format	units
{time} - Time t	seconds since the start of simulation	s
{T} - temperature		K
{Qv} - water vapor mixing ratio		kg/kg

{RH} - relative humidity w.r.t. water		%
{LWC} - liquid water content	defined as mass of liquid water per unit volume of dry air	$kg\ m^{-3}$
{IWC} - ice water content	defined as mass of ice water per unit volume of dry air	$kg\ m^{-3}$
{N_drop} - Droplet number concentration N_{drop}	A droplet is defined as a particle that has grown larger than the threshold radius, i.e., $r_{aerosol} > r_{threshold}$, where $r_{threshold}$ is the critical radius, here we set $r_{threshold} = 3.5\ \mu m$	m^{-3}
{N_ice} - ice number concentration N_{ice}	total number of ice particles	m^{-3}
{N_aerosol} - aerosol number concentration	Defined as the number of aerosols (not including INP) which are unactivated: $r_{aerosol} < r_{threshold} = 3.5\ \mu m$	m^{-3}
{N_drop_removal} - droplet removal rate	removal rate of droplet particles due to sedimentation and particle loss to the wall	$m^{-3}\ sec^{-1}$
{N_ice_removal} - droplet removal rate	removal rate of ice particles due to sedimentation and particle loss to the wall	$m^{-3}\ sec^{-1}$
{M_drop_removal} - liquid mass removal rate	removal rate of total liquid mass due to sedimentation and particle loss to the wall (i.e., including removal of all liquid particles, not using any truncated radius)	$kg\ m^{-3}\ sec^{-1}$
{M_ice_removal} - ice mass removal	removal rate of total ice mass due to sedimentation and particle loss to the wall	$kg\ m^{-3}\ sec^{-1}$
{disp_r} - relative dispersion of droplet size distribution	Defined as ratio between the standard deviation of droplet size distribution and the mean droplet size $= \frac{\sqrt{\Sigma(r - \bar{r})^2 / N_{drop}}}{\bar{r}}$	
{r_dmean} - droplet mean radius	$= \Sigma r_d / N_{drop}$	μm

{r_imean} - ice mean radius	$= \Sigma r_i / N_{ice}$	μm
{Sigma2_S_drop} - spatial variance of supersaturation with respect to liquid, $\sigma^2 S$	variance of the Eulerian field	
{Sigma2_S_ice} - spatial variance of supersaturation with respect to ice, $\sigma^2 S$	variance of the Eulerian field	
{Sigma2_T} - spatial variance of temperature, $\sigma^2 T$	variance of the Eulerian field	
{Sigma2_Qv} - spatial variance of water vapor mixing ratio, $\sigma^2 Qv$	variance of the Eulerian field	
{epsilon} - eddy dissipation rate ϵ	EDR at the bulk (core) region	$m^2 s^{-3}$
The variables below are required for models simulating entire chamber		
{TKE}	TKE of the bulk (core) domain	$m^2 s^{-2}$
{H_flux_t} - heat flux at the top	Fluxes near the top, bottom, side walls. Sidewall fluxes are preferred to collect if the model provides a way to calculate it.	Wm^{-2}
{H_flux_b} - heat flux at the bottom		
{H_flux_s} - heat flux at the sidewalls		
{qv_flux_t} - moisture flux at the top		
{qv_flux_b} - moisture flux at the bottom		
{qv_flux_s} - moisture flux at the sidewalls		$kg kg^{-1} ms^{-1}$
<p><i>The above time series of variables can be saved in a single file, filename: <u>AAA Nxxx_ID</u>, AAA is model name (DNS, LES, etc); xxx is the injection rate (e.g, 001, 010, 100...)</i></p>		

1.2) PSDs for droplets and ice (number concentration of each bin, time) at the end of the liquid spin-up period and at the end of the simulation at **every 30s**

{dsd1} - <i>DSD(r, t1)</i>	droplet size distribution at the end of liquid spin-up period. The first dimension of the array contains the number concentration of each droplet size bin; The second dimension is time. You may include several DSDs if there is no steady-state DSD established in your simulations. (Data format example: Time(s) bin1 bin2 bin3 bin4 ... 1000.00 100 20 10 15 ... 0.010 1030.00 102 23 13 13 ... 0.008 ...) 	cm^{-3} (number concentration in each bin). PSD output bin in linear scale: Bin width = 0.5 μm ,
{dsd2} - <i>DSD(r, t2)</i>	droplet size distribution at the end of the mixed-phase period. Same format as above.	range of radius from $r = 0 - 50 \mu m$
{isd} -ISD(r,t2)	ice size distribution at the end of the mixed-phase period.. same format as DSD.	.
<p><i>Saved in a separate file</i> <i>filename: <u>AAA_dsd1</u>, <u>AAA_dsd2</u>, <u>AAA_Nxxx_isd</u></i> <i>AAA is the model name (DNS, LES, etc); xxx is the INP injection rate (e.g, 001, 010, 100...)</i></p>		

2) 2D data (**height z, time t**) for models that simulate the entire chamber

2.1) mean vertical profile **at every 30s**. The value is averaged over the horizontal plane (also *exclude 4 points or 12.5cm from the sidewalls* when taking horizontal average).

Output variables	Output format	units
{time} - time		s
{z} - height	Distance from the bottom lid, please DO NOT exclude near wall region ($z=0-1m$)	m

{T} - temperature $T(z, t)$		K
{Qv} - $Qv(z, t)$		kg/kg
{RH} - $RH(z, t)$	relative humidity w.r.t. water	%
{LWC} - $LWC(z, t)$	Liquid water content	$kg\ m^{-3}$
{IWC} - $IWC(z, t)$	Ice water content	$kg\ m^{-3}$
<p><i>For netcdf output, the above time series of variables can be saved in a single file, filename: <u>AAA_Nxxx_2D</u>, AAA is model name (DNS, LES, etc); xxx is the INP injection rate (e.g, 001, 010, 100...);</i></p> <p><i>For ASCII files, each variable is saved in one file. Filename: <u>AAA_Nxxx_2D_var</u>, var is the name of the variable Data is saved in the following format: each row represents the profile at one time point, and each column is the time series at a given z location.</i></p>		

3) Simple plots for quick checkup and comparison (**for all models**)

Provide simple plots for quick checkup and comparison. Please include them along with the datasets:

- (1) 1D time series for each variable
- (2) 2D vertical profile plots for each variable (one profile at the end of the dynamic spin-up, one **before injecting ice**, one at the end of the simulation); **preferably taking some average of the profile to get the steady-state profile of each stage**
- (3) DSD at the end of simulation for each injection rate.

*Filename: AAA_Nxxx_1D, AAA_Nxxx_2D, AAA_Nxxx_dsd (in any readable **figure** format)*

Some example plots for the particle size PDF (but **droplet size distribution, rather than PDF, is preferred** for the intercomparison in order to compare the number concentrations) in warm-phase and mixed-phase conditions:

Fig. 4: Measured steady-state droplet radius PDFs in the Pi Chamber for different aerosol injection rates from the last Pi Chamber intercomparison case. This was a warm-phase case. The first number in the legend is the droplet number concentration (cm^{-3} }, the second is the injection rate ($cm^{-3} min^{-1}$)

Fig. 5: Measurements of PDF of mixed-phase particle diameters with different INP injection rates from PI Chamber. (Desai et al. 2019)

List of symbols

Symbol	Name of variable	Unit
Q_v	Water vapor mixing ratio	kg/kg
$Q_{v_t}, Q_{v_b}, Q_{v_s}$	Q_v at the top, bottom, and side wall	kg/kg
$Q_{v_{sat}}(T) = \epsilon \frac{e_{sat}(T)}{P - e_{sat}(T)}$	Q_v at saturated water vapor pressure $e_{sat} = Ae^{-B/T}$ is the saturated water vapor pressure. (eq. (2.12) in Rogers & Yau, 1989) $A=2.53e8$ kPa, $B=5.42e3$ K, $\epsilon \approx 0.615$	kg/kg
T_b, T_t, T_s	Temperature at the top and bottom, and side wall	K
ΔT	Temperature difference of the top and bottom	K

	walls	
P	Pressure inside the chamber	hPa
H=1	Height of the chamber	m
Lx, Ly=2	Width of the chamber in horizontal direction	m
dx, dz	Size of the grid box	m
$\sigma Qv, \sigma T$	Standard deviation of Qv and T	
S	Supersaturation ratio $S = \frac{e}{e_{sat}} - 1 \approx \frac{Qv}{Qv_{sat}(T)} - 1$	
d_{dry}	Diameter of the dry aerosol	μm
r_drop	Droplet radius	μm
r_ice	ice radius	μm
ϵ	Eddy dissipation rate	$m^2 s^{-3}$
U, V, W	Wind speed in x, y, z direction	$m s^{-1}$
N_{inj}	Aerosol injection rate	$m^{-3} sec^{-1}$
N_{drop}	Droplet number concentration	m^{-3}
N_{ice}	Ice number concentration	m^{-3}
e_{sat}	Saturated water vapor pressure	hPa
\bar{C}_d	Mean condensation rate	$kg kg^{-1} s^{-1}$

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